

Parental Involvement for Students' Academic Motivation at Secondary School Level

Zahoor Elahi¹, Shaista Mushtaq², Hassan Akhtar³

Abstract

The influence that parents have in their children's academic progress has long been recognized as critical. Parental involvement is a strategic essential to both conventional and modern methods of face-to-face education, including public/private schools and home schooling. The current study seeks to determine if this relationship exists in Pakistani schools, a country with significant educational challenges. The purpose of this study is to determine parental involvement and its influence on student academic motivation. In this study quantitative research approach is used. Survey by Questionnaire is conducted by utilizing reliable and valid instrument for parental Involvement mission. It comprises of parent's views about how to improve their children's schooling by using the factors which affecting the parental Involvement: Parental Belief, Family Environment, Parental Skills and Knowledge, Socio Economic status of Parents, Parental Attitude, Parental Level of Education, Family Motivation and Parent's Perceptions of General Invitations for Involvement from the School. A Simple Random sampling technique applied to select schools from district Sialkot. The students selected from high schools. Data were analyzed by using SPSS version 20. Factor analysis techniques used for the analysis of the data.. The result of this study shows high level of parental Involvement in children education will shows the high level of academic motivation among students at secondary school level.

Keywords: Parental involvement, Academic achievement, Secondary school level

1. Introduction

The involvement and struggle of parents in their children's educational attainment has long been seen to be crucial. Epstein, Sandars, Simon, Salinas, Jansorn, and Voorhis all agreed that parents play the most important influence in their children's educational achievements. No Child Left Behind Act (Epstein, 2018). Parental involvement is defined as parents' participation in regular, two-way, and meaningful communication involving academic learning and other school activities, such as: a. assisting their child's learning; b. being actively involved in their child's education at school; and c. serving as full partners in their child's education and being included, as appropriate, in decision-making and on advisory committees to assist in their child's education.

Family members provide the social, cultural, and emotional support that teenagers require to function healthily. Positive motivating concerns might be determined by an inspiring educational atmosphere that is responsive to the needs of youngsters (Malone and Lepper, 2021). On the other hand, negative motivational effects will have an undesirable influence on the environment. Children require social, cultural, and emotional support to fulfil their tasks in school. Positive motivation may be improved by providing a responsive educational atmosphere that is appropriate for the individual's requirements (Darling-Hammond and Cook-Harvey, 2018). Negative motivation, on the other hand, will create an unfavorable atmosphere. In our social system, school is the pivotal location that shapes children's interests, attitudes, and habits. Along with children's school regulation and academic accomplishment, the most dynamic factors are the teacher-child interaction, the safety established at school, and the parent's relationship at school (Alzahrani, Alharbi, and Alodwani, 2019).

According to Iishel and Ramirez, Parental Involvement is the involvement of a mother or father in their children's education with the goal of recognizing their educational and social achievements. Researchers, politicians, and educators have all acknowledged the importance of the PI function. Most scholars, including Walker, Hover-Dempsey, Whetsel, and Green agree that development in school success and interest in studies occurs when parents are involved in their children's education (Alzahrani, et al., 2019).

There is a link between children's performance and parents' struggles to support their education (Alzahrani, et al, 2019). It has been shown that parents who work hard and are interested in their child's education see their child's education develop. In general, the difficulties of the three agents-parents, school, and child-inspire one another. Similarly, children's ability to achieve better or battle for more is independent of their socioeconomic background. Some components of PI are included into a child's normal activities in schools around the United States and other nations. Children from better socioeconomic backgrounds do not always work harder than those from less wealthy backgrounds (Alzahrani, et al, 2019).

According to Crawford (2020), children go through significant developmental changes in elementary school, such as logical thinking, adaptation to their surroundings, and mannerism (Meade, 2011). Children build their social awareness in secondary school by integrating their information via relationships with instructors, peers, and families. Bamard felt that as students progressed through secondary school, they were more autonomous and formed relationships with a diverse group of people, including peers and educators (Meade, 2011). They also gain skills in a number of capacities.

¹MS Scholar, Department of Education, University of Sialkot, Sialkot, Pakistan

²MS Scholar, Department of Education, University of Sialkot, Sialkot, Pakistan

³MS Scholar, Department of Education, University of Sialkot, Sialkot, Pakistan

When parents become interested in children's education, they are much more likely to get involved in throughout their children's school years. According to Ferguson, when parents learn activities and routines at school, they can continue them at home, which helps their children's brain development. Parental involvement is critical for student development and has many advantages (Meade, 2011). It also aids in the improvement of classroom behavior. Students feel more motivated in class when their parents and teachers communicate more; their self-esteem and attitudes in class improve. Parental involvement improves academic performance while also having a positive impact on student attitude and behavior. A child's attitude toward school, classroom conduct, self-esteem, absenteeism, and motivation can all be influenced by a parent's involvement and encouragement in their child's education (Rubio, 2021).

Few national and international analyses of the influence of parental involvement on children's secondary school success have been conducted in this research (Gan & Bilige, 2019). The majority of research focused on the impact of socioeconomic status on success. There is few research that show the cause and impact of parental involvement in schooling. They are considered as the pillars of the country's whole educational programmed (Marciniak, 2018). As a result, this research was done to assess parental involvement in children's learning and its influence on their accomplishment at the secondary school level.

Students' academic success greatly influenced by their parents' socioeconomic status and involvement in their academic life. Irrespective of the parents' educational experiences, their support helps the children increase confidence in education and life. The importance of parental involvement in children's education cannot be overstated. When parents and teachers work together, children's educational interests are best served. Their combined efforts bring a number of benefits to both home and school. Cooperation that works successfully.

Besides that, the importance of the parental involvement in their children's education the socioeconomic issues and the attention of the parents directly affects the children's education. Specially in Pakistan, the idea of parental involvement in children's education is effective due to the socioeconomic states. In many developing countries, there is no policy regarding parental involvement in their children's education, same as in Pakistan. lack of school services and teacher's cynical attitude are putting parents off from being involved in children's education. Unprofessional teachers are not appreciating the parents' involvement and behind their unprofessionalism some factors are responsible like as lack of professional trainings and monitoring system.

The present study motivates and encourages the parents to involve in the study matters of their children. It proves the benefits of the Parental involvement on Student's Academic Achievement. Parental participation in their child's education has consistently been related to higher academic achievement. The findings demonstrated a statistically significant relationship between parental participation and a child's academic achievement, in addition to the influence of the child's interest.

1.1. Research Objective

- To explore parental involvement for students' academic motivation at secondary school level.

2. Review of Related Literature

Traditionally, parental involvement in education has received widespread recognition. Parents always want the best for their children and hope that they will enjoy a better life than they did. Several school-improvement programs have been undertaken in the modern age to promote children's learning. Parental Involvement is a multifaceted paradigm that has resulted in a variety of approaches. The survey of literature begins with a brief discussion of definitions.

The degree to which parents should be promised in the educational experiences of their children is fast becoming a subject of debate that is receiving a growing amount of attention in both educational policy and research. The findings of this study indicate that there may be a favorable link between the engagement of parents and academic success, especially during the years spent in secondary school. On the other hand, the existing body of research about the nature and level of the consequences of parental participation in secondary school is fragmented and has a limited scope of application. The bulk of the prior research has concentrated its efforts on the investigation of parental involvement in primary and secondary education (Hill, Witherspoon, and Bartz, 2018). There hasn't been a lot of study carried out on the question of how successful parental involvement may be in secondary schools.

The present study aims to raise awareness of the numerous activities that parents who have children enrolled in secondary school engage in, in addition to the repercussions that these practices have on the academic accomplishment of children who are enrolled in secondary education. Parents have a significant impact on their children's life in a variety of settings, including the home and the classroom. This relationship maintains true despite the fact that the youngster may be participating in a variety of different programs (Spencer, Gowdy, Drew, & Rhodes, 2019). The establishment of connections between educational institutions, families, and communities is advantageous for a number of different reasons. They have the ability to improve school programming as well as the atmosphere of the school, provide services and support for families, strengthen the skills and leadership abilities of parents, link families with others in the school and the community, and provide assistance to teachers in the performance of their duties. Nevertheless, the most essential motivation to develop partnerships of this sort is to increase students' prospects of being successful in school and in their lives after graduation (Noor-Ul-Amin, 2013).

The idea of parental involvement can be broken down into four distinct categories: involvement of parents in their children's activities that take place at school; involvement of parents in their children's activities that take place at home; involvement of parents directly in the academic pursuits of their children; and involvement of parents indirectly in the academic pursuits of their children. Involvement of parents in their children's activities that take place at home is the most common form of parental involvement. It is accurate to state that various parents take involved in the lives of their children to differing degrees depending on the circumstances. Consider, for example, a woman who is a parent to young children, as well as the level of education, or lack thereof, of the parents, the degree to which the father is involved, the financial situation of the family, the history of the family, and the social environment. All of these factors can have an impact. It has been established that parental participation with children from a young age is associated with better results, especially in the process of developing their personalities. This correlation was discovered via observation. Because parents are their children's major sources of guidance, the children attempt to model their behavior after their parents and believe that their parents are always correct (Kildare & Middlemiss, 2017). This gives the parents the opportunity to have as much influence as they possibly can on their children's lives. Even when other aspects of a child's life, such as their socioeconomic standing and the number of members in their family, are taken into account, parents' involvement continues to be a positive factor in their children's academic achievement. This remains true even after taking all of these other considerations into account.

It is possible that parental engagement in their kids' school-based actions is of the utmost importance. These actions may include contacting the children's instructors, verifying the children's attendance at school, keeping track of the children's activities while they are there, and reviewing the children's periodic academic progress reports. All of these items have the potential to be of great assistance in elevating children's academic performance to greater levels. When their children enter secondary schools, the educational possibilities available to them as parents become a greater concern. As children progress from basic school to central school and then on to secondary school, parents often find that the educational expectations they have for their children begin to take shape. Parents grow increasingly concerned about their children's postsecondary education and the impact that their children's secondary school programs will have on their children's possibilities for higher education as their children progress through their schooling.

3. Models of Parental Involvement

There are two models of parental involvement are discussed; Epstein's Framework of Six Types of Involvement; The method of Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler

3.1. Epstein's Framework of Six Types of Involvement

When it comes to identifying parental engagement practices and correlating them with different sorts' outcomes, one of the most helpful tools that the field has established so far is Epstein's framework of six basic forms of parental participation. This widely used framework was developed to assist educators in the formation of all-encompassing relationships between families and schools

It is recommended that educators, as well as parents, pick those techniques that are most likely to provide the sorts of results that correlate the most closely with their requirements, objectives, and capabilities. Epstein stresses the point that not all forms of parental involvement led to improvements in academic performance (Newman, Northcutt, Farmer, & Black, 2019). The outcomes that were chosen (one for each of the six different categories) should help dispel the common misconception that any practice that engages families would result in higher achievement test scores for children.

3.1.1. Parenting

It is the duty of schools to backing families in the growth of home settings that are conducive to learning by supplying parents with knowledge on topics such as children's health and nutrition, methods of punishment, the requirements of teenagers, and parenting styles. At the same time, schools have a responsibility to make an effort to learn about and include parts of the home lives of their pupils into the curriculum that is followed (Remillard & Jackson, 2018). The difficulty for schools is to make certain that all families who have a requirement for this kind of information receive it in an acceptable manner. Improvements in kids' conduct, school attendance, abilities in time management, and knowledge of the significance of school are some of the outcomes connected with type one activities. First and foremost, among the results that are connected to teachers is a greater knowledge of, and respect for, the families of their pupils.

3.1.2. Communicating

These include meetings between the parents and teachers, phone calls between the two, and report cards. Some schools need parental signatures on contracts that outline the obligations that must be met by the student body, the teaching staff, and the parents. Students will have a better knowledge of their own academic progress, will be able to make more informed decisions about the courses they enroll in, and will have a better comprehension of the school regulations that are connected to their behavior if they participate in type two activities.

It is expected that parents will increase their level of comprehension regarding school regulations and initiatives (Betancur, Votruba-Drzal, & Schunn, 2018). They will become more accustomed to communicating with the instructors at their children's schools, which will increase their capacity to monitor their children's growth and

respond to any issues that arise. It is anticipated of teachers that they will create a variety of techniques for connecting with parents, as well as the capacity to access the parent network in order to elicit family perspectives on the development of students.

3.1.3. Volunteering

Schools strengthen their relationships to the communities they serve by encouraging family members to participate in extracurricular activities, as well as to attend school-sponsored events. Volunteering is a great way for families to get to know their children's instructors and get more comfortable in the school environment (Arce, 2019). Volunteering initiatives at schools that capitalize on the skills of parents strengthen educational programs and, especially in the upper grades, facilitate students' ability to learn on their own terms. It is recommended, particularly at the secondary school level, to make use of a volunteer coordinator since it becomes increasingly difficult to coordinate the skills and availability of volunteers with the requirements of teachers and students. It can be difficult for schools to come up with a definition of "volunteer" that is inclusive of a wide enough, skills, and availability. They are also tasked with the responsibility of encouraging students to volunteer in their communities as an integral component of the educational experience.

The activities that fall into the category known as type three are intended to improve students' abilities to communicate with adults, to expose them to a wide range of adult skills, occupations, and other topics, and to assist students in the development of their own skills with the assistance of volunteer tutors and mentors. As a consequence of the assistance provided by volunteers, classroom instructors will finally have more time to devote to the education of individual pupils (Back, Han, & Weng, 2020). In addition to this, it is anticipated that they will grow more receptive to involve parents in a variety of different ways and will acquire a respect for the parental talent base.

3.1.4. Learning at Home

The majority of parental involvement in their children's educational experiences takes place at home. It is important for schools to work on increasing the level of comprehension that parents have of the content of the curriculum as well as the abilities that their children are expected to acquire at each successive stage of their education. In addition, schools have a responsibility to show parents about the various monitoring methods they use for kids, as well as any other policies or procedures, so that parents may participate in decision-making processes that are in their kids' best interests.

Activities of this type have the potential to assist bridge any cultural or social divide that may exist between the home and the school setting (Joyce & Cartwright, 2020). Because of this, educational institutions have the problem of developing a menu of interactive projects that makes use of the support abilities of parents and incorporates them into the learning processes. Additionally, schools and parents need to collaborate in order to ensure that kids define academic objectives, are well prepared for career transitions, and choose the proper classes.

Results connected with type four activities include improvements in students' results on standardized tests as well as other abilities related to homework. Students also have a greater propensity to consider themselves as students and to view their parents in a teaching role. The completion of additional homework and a more positive attitude toward academic responsibilities are both connected with type four activities (Herodotou, Rienties, Boroowa, Zdrahal, & Hlosta, 2019). It's possible for parents to start seeing their kids as more of a learning resource, which may help them feel more confident in their own ability to instruct and provide support for their kids' educational endeavors. In addition to this, they are more likely to engage in conversations on their children's schooling. The use of type four techniques can assist educators in the creation of more useful homework assignments. When instructors see the support that different kinds of families are able to give their pupils, one of the things that is anticipated of them is that they will acquire a stronger level of satisfaction with the family engagement programmed.

3.1.5. Decision-making

One further tactic that may be used to strengthen the ties that bind schools and parents together is to give parents a voice in school governance, decision-making, and advocacy positions. As parental engagement in decision-making is related with higher student results, it is also associated with improved student outcomes when the programmed in question is comprehensive and involves parents in learning support activities (Tan, Lyu, & Peng, 2020). The advantages accrued to pupils as a result of the implementation of various policies are one of the outcomes of type five activities.

3.1.6. Collaborating with the Community

In order to be successful in their mission to educate children, schools and families need to routinely seek help from community resources. When working together, families, schools, and other community groups and leaders may achieve the highest success for their students (Jeynes, 2018). More chances are afforded to children for learning and for making connections between what they learn in school and their experiences in the wider world. They surround themselves with people besides their parents and instructors who instill in them the value of education and encourage them to continue to grow in shows actually.

One of the outcomes linked with type six activities is a growth in students' abilities and talents, provided that they participate in constructive extracurricular programs (Shaffer, 2019). Students could also get a deeper comprehension of the actual world and the various professional paths available to them. The understanding of

local resources that a parent may tap into to help them is one of the outcomes associated to parenting. children and families are prioritized. They will also have a greater propensity to engage in social activity with other families residing in the neighborhood. It is expected of teachers that they will gain a comprehension of the resources that are accessible to improve the curriculum. They should also have the ability to collaborate with a wide array of community partners and utilize their resources.

3.2. Parental involvement method of Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler

Parental engagement in their children's informative experiences is widely recognized as an important aspect, relatively little is understood regarding the psychological variables that drive parental involvement practices (Marchand, Vassar, Diemer, & Rowley, 2019). When considering the process of parent participation from the point of view of the parents, the most important particular aspects to concentrate on are the following: Several explanations.

3.2.1. Reasons of parental Involvement

The model is able to handle the process of parent participation in a way that is both multidimensional and dynamic. They provided a structure for their model in order to show and investigate the parent engagement process in a more comprehensive manner. They established five degrees of parent engagement in this model as a way to respond to the issues that were raised before regarding the involvement of parents. The ecological systems theory developed by Bronfenbrenner (1979) provided inspiration for a number of the components of each of these five levels.

Children acquire important life skills within the context of their families. These include the ability to make decisions, to take responsibility for their actions, to respect the feelings and opinions of others, to express and receive love, to fulfil social roles, to be creative, and to begin their formal education. When it comes to bringing up their children, parents employ a variety of approaches, each of which is based on a distinct set of attitudes and actions.

The perspectives and actions that parents take may shift over time as a result of changes in their personal traits (Mayer, Kalil, Oreopoulos, & Gallegos, 2019), the social and psychological circumstances in which they find themselves, the characteristics of their children, and the actions that those children do. All of these distinct factors drive parents to behave in a variety of ways, which ultimately shape their approach to parenting. The manner in which a kid is raised may significantly impact both their public and instructive development. The term "parenting style" refers to a mental structure that symbolizes the normal tactics that parents utilize in the process of child upbringing. This structure also includes the attitudes and actions of the parents.

The perspective that the parent takes on the kid is one of the factors that might influence the individual's capacity to learn (Bell, Clarke, Mounier-Jack, Walker, & Paterson, 2020). The accomplishment goal orientation is yet another idea that is associated with student achievement. When seen in this light, it is possible to assert that the accomplishment goal orientation of students has an effect on the ways in which they behave while at school and the various learning techniques that they employ. These distinctions are also reflected in the academic achievements of the kids.

The perspectives and actions that parents take when they are raising their children have a huge influence not only on the behaviors that children will exhibit in the future but also on the behaviors that children exhibit at younger ages. In order for children to be able to demonstrate consistent behaviors in society, to be self-sufficient, to acquire the essential social skills, and to reach his or her independence, it is imperative that they have healthy connections with their parents. This has a strong connection to the mentalities and actions of one's parents, or more specifically, the parenting strategies that are utilized.

3.2.2. Academic Motivation

Young children, including infants and toddlers, have a built-in curiosity about the how and whys of the world around them. Some kids, after having more and more unfavorable experiences in school, grow to believe that their efforts will not be rewarded and, as a result, they quit putting in as much effort. Numerous studies have demonstrated that, as children progress through school, they experience a gradual decline in their desire to learn new things. Learning and motivation are both significantly influenced by a wide variety of circumstances. It has been established that the atmosphere of the school, the attitudes and views of instructors, as well as the values held by families and the community, are significant elements that influence the motivation of students.

This article focuses on the motivation of students because of its direct connection to school engagement and academic growth, despite the fact that these components are extremely crucial for comprehending the actions of students while they are in school. Both instructors and guidance counsellors at schools are in a prime position to see when students are struggling with their motivation and to take corrective action to address the issue. Therefore, they need to be ready to support kids who are in need of enhancements to their motivation. Following an overview of several motivating factors that research has proven to have an impact on students' levels of motivation, the following sections provide an introduction to various tactics for boosting students' levels of academic motivation. Research have constantly been conducted over the past few decades to investigate the motivational underpinnings of student behavior. The empirical findings of these studies have shown evidence of a substantial association between the academic functioning of students and their level of motivation. These motivational components include objectives, values, intrinsic vs extrinsic motivation, beliefs and perceptions, and goals. First, the writers

give definitions of the motivational structures and empirical evidence of the links between these traits and learning outcomes. Next, the authors present theoretical viewpoints of motivation that these motivational constructs have been formed from. The new terminologies could appear to be quite daunting to readers who are not well versed in the concepts and theories pertaining to motivation. Nevertheless, the readers of these introductions are simply given a cursory overview of these motivational components, despite the fact that research has shown that they are beneficial to learning.

4. Research Methodology

The foremost motive of the research was to explore the parental involvement for students' academic motivation at secondary school level in district Sialkot. Parents' better understanding about the position of parental involvement (PI) in students' academic motivation at secondary school level, according to the researchers, is a contemporary issue to be addressed. It was decided to devise a quantitative research design because quantitative research involves collecting and analyzing numerical data to understand better, predict and regulate phenomena of interest (Andrew, Pedersen, and McEvoy, 2019). Therefore, the descriptive research method was used, in order to achieve the research objective, the researchers used an approach which is a strategy for collecting, mixing, analyzing, and integrating quantitative data. It is stated that the study was based on the idea of exploring the parental involvement and students' academic motivation as well as the awareness and use of parenting techniques to their children at the secondary school level (Papadakis, Zaranis, and Kalogiannakis, 2019).

All the secondary school students who were studying at grade 9 and 10 in district Sialkot constituted the population of the study. The researcher used simple random sampling technique for the selection of sample from the population of the study. Cohen, Manion and Monson prescribed the sample size will be 372 if the population size will be more than 10,000. Furthermore, researcher discussed with supervisor and experts related to this research, it was decided to take the sample of 300 secondary school students from all the four tehsils of the district Sialkot. The researchers developed a self-constructed questionnaire for students because researchers used research tool to meet the objectives of the study and the researcher selected questionnaire as research tool. For constructing of questionnaire, the researcher firstly searches and collected the thesis related to the Parental involvement and academic motivation through the literature review, furthermore, the researchers collected data and statements related to research topic and objectives and they explored 9 factors having 3 items for each factor.

Pilot testing was approved to determine whether the items contained in the questionnaire were relevant, easily understandable, and straightforward. Following the original creation of the questionnaire were edited. After discussion with ten education experts and research supervisors, the research instrument was refined due to the pilot testing findings and the study's conclusion. All the items of the questionnaire were taken into consideration before the actual launch. Questionnaire's statements were typed so that the statement would become clear and understandable when printed out on a page. Respondents were allowed to "mark" their answer.

For this purpose, researchers tried out the questionnaire at 50 teachers. Questionnaire for students were handed over to 50 students for their observation. Following the inclusion and preparation of drafts of questions, which were discussed with experts in the relevant subject, some questions were omitted from the draughts and others were included. The final draughts of the questionnaire were discussed and approved again with the assistance of specialists before being fair typed and photocopies. The reliability of the test items in the study's tool was tested using the SPSS software. Which the researchers developed. The study's research tool consisted of 27 items. The association between the scores of even and odd test items was statistically significant.

Through personal visits and use of social media i.e. facebook educational groups, WhatsApp groups, and Google form the researchers distributed the questionnaires to the 472 questionnaires to secondary school students. The researchers personally visited the four tehsils of district Sialkot for the collection of data. The analysis of the data is a critical component of the entire investigation. Statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) was used to record the data gathered. The data was initially handled in Microsoft Excel and then transferred to SPSS. Factor analysis, mean score and standard deviation were used and then interpreted to achieve the objective set for the study.

5. Data Analysis and Interpretation

5.1. Factor Analysis

The table 1 informed about the "parental belief" about students' motivation and their Academic achievement. The value of mean sum (4.247) and standard deviation shows that majority of the respondents positively agree behave with factor parental believes. P= Percent and F= Frequency

The table 2 informed about the "Family Environment" about students' motivation and their Academic achievement. The value of mean sum (4.093) and standard deviation shows that majority of the respondents positively agree behave with factor family environment.

Table 1: Parental Belief

Sr No	Factor	Values	♁	♂	Mean	S. D
1	Parental Belief	2.8	1	0.3	4.247	0.448
		3	1	0.3		
		3.2	6	2		
		3.4	5	1.7		
		3.6	18	6		
		3.8	45	15		
		4	37	12.3		
		4.2	35	11.7		
		4.4	59	19.7		
		4.6	45	15		
		4.8	26	8.7		
Total		5	22	7.3		
			300	100		

Table 2: Family Environment

Sr No	Factor	Values	♁	♂	Mean	S. D
2	Family Environment	2.4	1	0.3	4.093	0.525
		2.6	3	1		
		2.8	2	0.7		
		3	9	3		
		3.2	15	5		
		3.4	14	4.7		
		3.6	15	5		
		3.8	35	11.7		
		4	42	14		
		4.2	45	15		
		4.4	45	15		
		4.6	44	14.7		
		4.8	24	8		
		5	6	2		
Total			300	100		

Table 3: Parental Skills and Knowledge

Sr No	Factor	values	♁	♂	Mean	S. D
3	Parental Skills and Knowledge	1.4	2	0.7	4.314	0.561
		1.8	1	0.3		
		2.2	2	0.7		
		2.4	1	0.3		
		3	4	1.3		
		3.2	6	2		
		3.4	2	0.7		
		3.6	11	3.7		
		3.8	28	9.3		
		4	17	5.7		
		4.2	33	11		
		4.4	69	23		
		4.6	61	20.3		
		4.8	34	11.3		
5	29	9.7				
Total			300	100		

The above-mentioned table 3 informed about the “Parental Skills and Knowledge” about students’ motivation and their Academic achievement. The value of mean sum (4.314) and standard deviation shows that majority of the respondents positively agree behave with factor parental skills and knowledge.

Table 4: Parents Socio-Economics Status

Sr No	Factor	values	ƒ	ƒ	Mean	S. D
		1	4	1.3		
		1.2	3	1		
		1.4	4	1.3		
		1.8	14	4.7		
		2	23	7.7		
		2.2	30	10		
		2.4	39	13		
4	Parental Socio-Economics Status	2.6	86	28.7	2.556	0.522
		2.8	41	13.7		
		3	20	6.7		
		3.2	16	5.3		
		3.4	12	4		
		3.6	3	1		
		4	2	0.7		
		4.4	1	0.3		
		4.6	2	0.7		
	Total		300	100		

The above-mentioned table 4 informed about the “Parental Socio-Economics Status” about students’ motivation and their Academic achievement. The value of mean sum (2.556) and standard deviation (0.522) shows that majority of the respondents positively agree behave with factor parental socio-economic status.

Table 5: Parental Attitude

Sr No	Factor	values	ƒ	ƒ	Mean	S. D
		2	1	0.3		
		2.2	1	0.3		
		2.4	3	1		
		2.6	1	0.3		
		2.8	1	0.3		
		3	17	5.7		
		3.2	6	2		
5	Parental Attitudes	3.4	20	6.7	4.004	0.65
		3.6	30	10		
		3.8	40	13.3		
		4	47	15.7		
		4.2	43	14.3		
		4.4	31	10.3		
		4.6	23	7.7		
		4.8	23	7.7		
		5	13	4.3		
	Total		300	100		

The above-mentioned table 5 informed about the “Parental Attitudes” about students’ motivation and their Academic achievement. The value of mean sum (4.004) and standard deviation (0.65) shows that Majority of the respondents positively agree behave with factor Parental Attitudes.

Table 6: Parental Level of Education

Sr No	Factor	values	♣	♠	Mean	S. D
		1.4	1	0.3		
		1.6	1	0.3		
		1.8	3	1		
		2	1	0.3		
		2.2	1	0.3		
		2.4	1	0.3		
		2.6	5	1.7		
		2.8	2	0.7		
		3	2	0.7		
6	Parental level of Education	3.2	9	3	3.889	0.56
		3.4	28	9.3		
		3.6	36	12		
		3.8	54	18		
		4	42	14		
		4.2	48	16		
		4.4	37	12.3		
		4.6	19	6.3		
		4.8	7	2.3		
		5	3	1		
		Total	300	100		

The above-mentioned table 6 informed about the “Parental level of Education” about students’ motivation and their Academic achievement. The value of mean sum (3.889) and standard deviation (0.56) shows that Majority of the respondents positively agree behave with factor Parental level of Education.

Table 7: Intrinsic Motivation

Sr No	Factor	values	♣	♠	Mean	S. D
		2.5	2	0.7		
		2.75	2	0.7		
		3	4	1.3		
		3.25	14	4.7		
		3.5	10	3.3		
7	Intrinsic Motivation	3.75	25	8.3	4.295	0.514
		4	28	9.3		
		4.25	63	21		
		4.5	76	25.3		
		4.75	40	13.3		
		5	36	12		
		Total	300	100		

The above-mentioned table 7 informed about the “Intrinsic Motivation” about students’ motivation and their Academic achievement. The value of mean sum (4.295) and standard deviation (0.514) shows that Majority of the respondents positively agree behave with factor Intrinsic Motivation.

Table 8: Extrinsic Motivation

Sr No	Factor	values	ƒ ₁	ƒ ₂	Mean	S. D
		2.33	1	0.3		
		2.5	4	1.3		
		2.83	4	1.3		
		3	3	1		
		3.17	5	1.7		
		3.33	9	3		
		3.5	21	7		
8	Extrinsic Motivation	3.67	26	8.7	4.088	0.521
		3.83	32	10.7		
		4	35	11.7		
		4.17	39	13		
		4.33	30	10		
		4.5	42	14		
		4.67	23	7.7		
		4.83	14	4.7		
		5	12	4		
		Total	300	100		

The above-mentioned table 8 informed about the “Extrinsic Motivation” about students’ motivation and their Academic achievement. The value of mean sum (4.088) and standard deviation (0.521) shows that Majority of the respondents positively agree behave with factor Extrinsic Motivation.

Table 9: Family Motivation

Sr No	Factor	Values	ƒ ₁	ƒ ₂	Mean	S. D
		1.75	3	1		
		2	1	0.3		
		2.25	7	2.3		
		2.5	18	6		
		2.75	12	4		
		3	21	7		
9	Family Motivation	3.25	57	19	3.552	0.647
		3.5	52	17.3		
		3.75	39	13		
		4	33	11		
		4.25	21	7		
		4.5	20	6.7		
		4.75	12	4		
		5	4	1.3		
		Total	300	100		

The above-mentioned table 9 informed about the “Family Motivation” about students’ motivation and their Academic achievement. The value of mean sum (3.552) and standard deviation (0.647) shows that Majority of the respondents positively agree behave with factor Family Motivation.

6. Findings and Conclusions

Findings of the current study have been from the analysis of the collected data. Findings are as under; The study found that most of the parents (76.70%) knows the abilities of their children and in this way they support their children academically. Furthermore, they train their children for asking the questions. The study also found that most of the parent know about the healthy feeling and actions of their children, so that it helps them for academic motivation. In this study it is found that 90.40% parents parenting styles improve their children’s skills. It is also

discovered that parents lifestyle effects their children's manner that provide motivation for their academic life. The study also found that most of the student's (79.70%) learning activities affects by their family atmosphere, whereas most of the students communication skills effected by their parents quarrels. It is revealed that most of the parents monitor their children's academic activities that are very much beneficial for their academic motivation. While students family size influence their academic performance at school level.

The study provides the result that parents' (86.30%) participations encourage the students' learning activities and students learning abilities enhance by their family education. On the other hand, students academic motivation is improved by parents skills and in this perspective students get the opportunity to improve their reading and writing skills at school level. It is an important fact that parents' knowledge and skills inspire students for academic motivation while the students get awareness about technological tools that is helpful for 21st century students. Student socio-economic status have a deeper effect on students' confidence and it is also important that most of the parents fulfil the educational necessities of their children. It's a great thing that most of the parents provide books to their children that definitely inspire students' academic motivation. Most of the parents feel proud when their children perform well while the parents appreciate their children take an initiative.

It is important for our educational system that most of the illiterate parents understand their children's educational needs. On contrary, the study found that family education become a source of inspiration and trigger students' academic motivation for future successes in academics and ultimately it makes positive effects for students' educational progress.

The study concluded that that there was a significant level of parental involvement in children's schooling. There was a favorable association between parental involvement and student accomplishment. These findings corroborated prior studies that found that parental participation has a favorable influence on children' subject mastery and accomplishment. In addition to performance on standardized testing and academic examinations, Furthermore, parental participation has been linked to less behavioral issues in school, greater attendance and class preparation, better course completion, and reduced dropout rates.

6.1. Recommendations

According to the Pakistani context parental involvement is very fruitful for the betterment of student's academic achievement. So, the study may recommended that evolving skills of teachers / educators may involve the parents through 21st century modern gadgets and strategies for students' academic motivation at school level.

References

- Alzahrani, M., Alharbi, M., & Alodwani, A. (2019). The Effect of Social-Emotional Competence on Children Academic Achievement and Behavioral Development. *International Education Studies*, 12(12), 141-149.
- Arce, S. (2019). Exploring Parent and Teacher Perceptions of Family Engagement. *International Journal of Teacher Leadership*, 10(2), n2.
- Back, M., Han, M., & Weng, S.-C. (2020). Emotional scaffolding for emergent multilingual learners through translanguaging: Case stories. *Language and education*, 34(5), 387-406.
- Bell, S., Clarke, R., Mounier-Jack, S., Walker, J. L., & Paterson, P. (2020). Parents' and guardians' views on the acceptability of a future COVID-19 vaccine: A multi-methods study in England. *Vaccine*, 38(49), 7789-7798.
- Betancur, L., Votruba-Drzal, E., & Schunn, C. (2018). Socioeconomic gaps in science achievement. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 5(1), 1-25.
- Crawford, M. (2020). Ecological Systems theory: Exploring the development of the theoretical framework as conceived by Bronfenbrenner. *J Pub Health Issue Pract*, 4(2), 170.
- Epstein, J. L. (2018). *School, family, and community partnerships: Preparing educators and improving schools*: Routledge.
- Gan, Y., & Bilige, S. (2019). Parental involvement in home-based education and children's academic achievement in China. *Social Behavior and Personality: an international journal*, 47(12), 1-15.
- Herodotou, C., Rienties, B., Boroowa, A., Zdrahal, Z., & Hlosta, M. (2019). A large-scale implementation of predictive learning analytics in higher education: the teachers' role and perspective. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 67(5), 1273-1306.
- Hill, N. E., Witherspoon, D. P., & Bartz, D. (2018). Parental involvement in education during middle school: Perspectives of ethnically diverse parents, teachers, and students. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 111(1), 12-27.
- Jeynes, W. H. (2018). A practical model for school leaders to encourage parental involvement and parental engagement. *School Leadership & Management*, 38(2), 147-163.
- Joyce, K. E., & Cartwright, N. (2020). Bridging the gap between research and practice: Predicting what will work locally. *American Educational Research Journal*, 57(3), 1045-1082.
- Kildare, C. A., & Middlemiss, W. (2017). Impact of parents mobile device use on parent-child interaction: A literature review. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 75, 579-593.
- Malone, T. W., & Lepper, M. R. (2021). Making learning fun: A taxonomy of intrinsic motivations for learning. In *Aptitude, learning, and instruction* (pp. 223-254): Routledge.

- Marchand, A. D., Vassar, R. R., Diemer, M. A., & Rowley, S. J. (2019). Integrating race, racism, and critical consciousness in Black parents' engagement with schools. *Journal of Family Theory & Review*, 11(3), 367-384.
- Marciniak, R. (2018). Quality assurance for online higher education programmes: Design and validation of an integrative assessment model applicable to Spanish universities. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 19(2).
- Mayer, S. E., Kalil, A., Oreopoulos, P., & Gallegos, S. (2019). Using behavioral insights to increase parental engagement the parents and children together intervention. *Journal of Human Resources*, 54(4), 900-925.
- Meade, D. L. (2011). *Teacher and parent perspectives on proactive parental involvement with students with autism*. Walden University,
- Newman, N., Northcutt, A., Farmer, A., & Black, B. (2019). Epstein's model of parental involvement: Parent perceptions in urban schools. *Language Teaching and Educational Research*, 2(2), 81-100.
- Noor-Ul-Amin, S. (2013). An effective use of ICT for education and learning by drawing on worldwide knowledge, research, and experience. *ICT as a Change Agent for Education. India: Department of Education, University of Kashmir*, 1, 13.
- Papadakis, S., Zaranis, N., & Kalogiannakis, M. (2019). Parental involvement and attitudes towards young Greek children's mobile usage. *International Journal of Child-Computer Interaction*, 22, 100144.
- Remillard, J. T., & Jackson, K. (2018). Old math, new math: Parents' experiences with standards-based reform. In *Urban Parents' Perspectives on Children's Mathematics Learning and Issues of Equity in Mathematics Education* (pp. 231-259): Routledge.
- Rubio, F. (2021). *Self-esteem and foreign language learning*: Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
- Shaffer, M. L. (2019). Impacting student motivation: Reasons for not eliminating extracurricular activities. *Journal of Physical Education, Recreation & Dance*, 90(7), 8-14.
- Spencer, R., Gowdy, G., Drew, A. L., & Rhodes, J. E. (2019). "Who knows me the best and can encourage me the most?": Matching and early relationship development in youth-initiated mentoring relationships with system-involved youth. *Journal of Adolescent Research*, 34(1), 3-29.
- Tan, C. Y., Lyu, M., & Peng, B. (2020). Academic benefits from parental involvement are stratified by parental socioeconomic status: A meta-analysis. *Parenting*, 20(4), 241-287.